

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF STROKE HOSPITAL REGISTER IN TASHKENT CITY AND TASHKENT REGION

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ANNOTATION : Stroke is one of the most important medical and social problems in the field of health care in Uzbekistan and throughout the world. It is associated with a high prevalence of the disease, a high mortality rate and severe disability of patients. The problem of cerebrovascular diseases (CVD) remains very relevant due to the high morbidity, mortality and lethality, including acute cerebral stroke (ACS). Vascular diseases of the brain are the most important medical and social problem (Gusev E.I., Skvortsova V.I., Stakhovskaya JI.B., 2003, Suslina Z.A., 2008). This is due to the high prevalence, high mortality and severe consequences of the disease. Patients who survive are often severely disabled. This problem is also relevant for the CIS countries (Majidov N.M., 1998; 2000; Martinov E.I., 2001; Gusev E.I., 2002; Asadullaev M.M., 2002; Vereshchagin N.I., 2002; Ga., B. Juraev2.0.; Ga., B.2.0. 2003; Khodjaev A.I., 2003). In Uzbekistan, disability due to cerebral stroke is 3.2 disabled people per 10,000 population (Rakhimjonov A.R., 1997). In Uzbekistan, the incidence of stroke is 0.9 to 1.4 per 1000 inhabitants, and in Tashkent it is 1.5 (Rakhimjonov A.R., 1999; Asadullaev M.M., 2002)

About 400,000 people get a stroke in Russia every year (E.V. Oshchepkova, Yu.Ya. Varakin, 2000, N.V. Vereshchagin, Z.A. Suslina, 2006).

There are no official statistics on the incidence of stroke in Tashkent city and Tashkent region, so it is necessary to organize a stroke register to assess the epidemiological situation in a certain region. The stroke registry is the best way to

determine the effectiveness of measures to combat morbidity, mortality and stroke, as well as to assess the social and economic consequences of stroke (N.V.Vereshchagin, Yu.Ya.Varakin, 2002).

The purpose of the study:

According to the data of the stroke register in Tashkent city and region, to study the main epidemiological characteristics and to assess the presence of leading risk factors, clinical characteristics and to develop preventive measures based on them.

Research tasks:

1. Development of an electronic version of the hospital stroke register
2. Introduction of the electronic version of the stroke registry in large hospitals that receive stroke patients.
3. Analysis of the main epidemiological indicators: stroke incidence, death

Results and discussion. From September 1, 2020 to December 31, 2022, a stroke registry was conducted throughout the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region. In the first year of the study, 7,129 cases of stroke were recorded. In the second year of the study, 6,543 new and recurrent strokes were recorded. 13,672 stroke patients were registered during the entire study period: 7,014 of them were men (51.3%) and 6,658 were women (48.6%). The average age of stroke patients was 58.6 ± 5.4 years. In the first year of the study, 5029 cases were recorded in Tashkent, and in the second year, 4852 cases were recorded.

Of the total number of cerebral strokes, 3.8% occurred in young people (18-44 years old), 42% in middle-aged people (45-59 years old), 36.1% in old people (60-74 years old), and 18.1% in old people (75-90 years old). it's worth it. The relatively low incidence of MI in the elderly appears to be due to misdiagnosis due to the obscurity of disease symptoms.

List of references

1. Gusev E.I., Skvortsova V.I., Stakhovskaya L.V. i dr. Epidemiology stroke v Rossii // Consilium Medicum. Spets. vyp. "Neurology". 2003. S. 5-7.;

2. Suslina Z.A., Epidemiology stroke v Rossii // Consilium Medicum. "Neurology". 2008).
3. Gusev E.I. Epidemiology stroke v Rossii // Consilium Medicum. Spets. vyp. "Neurology". 2004. S. 25-27.;
4. Madjidov N.M.; International Journal of Experimental Education. 2000. No. 3-2. S. 59-64.
5. Gafurov B.G.; International Journal of Experimental Education. 2003. #2. S. 35-36.
6. Rakhimdjanov A.R., Vestnik Severo-Vostochnogo federalnogo universiteta im. M.K. Ammosova. Series: Medical science. 2001. No. 4 (09). S. 69-72.
7. Wolfe C., Giroud M., Kolominsky-Rabas P. et al. Variations in stroke incidence and survival in 3 areas of Europe //Stroke.2000.